

NOTES

A Rapid Method for the Determination of Lime in Cement and Various Calcareous Materials

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A rapid volumetric method for estimation of lime in cement and various calcareous materials is described. The method is based on opening the sample with a mixed solution of ammonium chloride and tartaric acid and subsequently estimating calcium titrimetrically by the oxalate method. The presence of silica, iron, aluminium, manganese (in part), sulphate, phosphate, and magnesium do not have any interfering effect.

It has been observed that limestone, dolomite, calcareous materials, cement, cement plaster, cement concrete (mortar portion), precipitated calcium phosphate, gypsum, etc. can be opened up quantitatively in the mixed solution of ammonium chloride and tartaric acid. The presence of tartaric acid in mixed solution also obviates interfering ions of the conventional method. These observations have been utilised in the present method.

EXPERIMENTAL

Reagents :

- (1) Potassium Permanganate (0.1*N*)
- (2) Standardisation : Permanganate solution is standardised against a standard solution of A.R. sodium oxalate.
- (3) Mixed Solution : Dissolve 150 g. of A.R. ammonium chloride and 60 g. of A.R. tartaric acid in water and make up to 1 litre (use freshly prepared).
- (4) Ammonium Oxalate : Saturated solution.
- (5) Ammonia : 10% v/v solution.
- (6) Wash solution : 2% v/v ammonia solution.
- (7) Methyl Red indicator : 0.1%
- (8) Sulphuric acid : 2*N*.

Procedure : Weigh accurately the dried (at 110°) sample, finely powdered, containing not more than 100 mg. of lime in a 400 ml dry pyrex beaker. Add, while stirring, 50 ml of mixed solution. Cover the beaker with a watch glass. Boil for 10 to 15 min, the sample goes into solution except silica. Break the lumps, if any, with a glass rod. Dilute the solution to 200 ml with water, heat to boiling and add while stirring 25 ml of a hot saturated solution of ammonium oxalate to precipitate calcium as calcium oxalate. Add methyl red indicator and then ammonia solution until it just turns yellow. Boil for 2 to 3 minutes. Keep the precipitate on water bath for half an hour and check for complete precipitation. Filter through Whatman No. 30 filter paper and wash the precipitate with a cold ammonia

wash solution until free from oxalate and chloride ions. Dissolve the precipitate in 2*N* sulphuric acid and titrate against standard permanganate solution to a pink end point which persists for 30 sec. Calculate lime from the titre value.

1 ml of 0.1*N* KMnO_4 = 28.00 mg of CaO = 20.04 mg of Ca.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

A perusal of the observations made on a series of different types of materials will thus show that the results obtained by the proposed method agree with those by conventional method within the limits of experimental error. Table I clearly shows that the method is

TABLE I

Comparison of results obtained by conventional and proposed method

Source of Lime.	Lime by conventional method	Lime by proposed method.
<i>Limestone</i>		
1.	46.20	46.30
2.	53.15	53.03
<i>Dolomite</i>		
1.	28.12	28.20
2.	30.58	30.49
<i>Cement</i>		
1.	60.89	60.98
2.	63.00	62.86
<i>Cement Plaster</i>		
1.	7.14	7.16
2.	9.80	9.77
<i>Cement Concrete : (Mortar Portion)</i>		
1.	10.15	10.18
2.	15.40	15.36
<i>Calcite</i>		
1.	54.89	54.95
2.	55.64	55.60
<i>Precipitated Calcium Phosphate (Pure Salt)</i>		
1.	54.18	54.22
<i>Gypsum (Pure Salt)</i>		
1	32.56	32.48

equally applicable over a wide range of concentration of lime in different materials. Whenever carbonaceous matter is suspected in the cement plaster and cement concrete (mortar portion), it is absolutely necessary to filter off the solution before precipitating calcium. The various ions which are usually associated with cement and various calcareous materials were tested for their interference. Keeping the concentration of lime constant, the effect of various interfering ions in different concentrations was studied. Table II shows that phosphate, manganese (in part), sulphate, iron, aluminium do not have any interfering effect.

TABLE II

Effect of various ions on the proposed method of lime estimation

	Ions added per 100 mg. of Lime	Lime Found (in mg).
Phosphate	5 mg.	99.98
	20 ,,	100.03
Manganese	5 ,,	100.80
	20 ,,	102.80
Sulphate	5 ,,	99.97
	20 ,,	99.96
Iron	5 ,,	100.00
	20 ,,	100.01
Aluminium	5 ,,	100.00
	20 ,,	100.00

The method proposed is thus not only applicable over a wide variety of cements and calcareous materials, but it takes a considerably less time than the conventional method because the necessity of prior removal of interfering ions has been eliminated.

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